
The Journey Of Digital Screens Changing The Purchasing Pattern

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Abstract:

The intersection of social media platforms and e-commerce systems helps in reshaping the digital economy of India. This research paper provides the framework of India's vision for 2047, using a conceptual model-based approach to understand its implications on digital transformation. Through this model, it studies the connectivity between three major components: social marketing, consumer behaviour, and e-commerce retail strategies. The proposed model simulates the connectivity and data-driven decisions and insights by social media platforms to analyse the shopping habits of the consumer. This study uses the survey method to gather the insights of purchasing patterns and platform analytics to validate the model. Through the designated survey, it would provide information about the significance of social media enhancing the e-commerce ecosystem. The research attempts to study how social media marketing has become a powerful tool in shaping consumer behaviour, providing a platform for businesses to connect with their target audience in a personalised and engaging manner. Through tailored content, influencer collaborations, and interactive campaigns, businesses earn a strong customer base and mutual trust. As the accessibility of social media gives consumers the right to have data-driven decisions for a product or service. The findings highlight the potential of a synergistic relationship between social media platforms and e-commerce systems influencing consumer behaviour. The study will help policymakers, businessmen, and governments to make policies and strategies to accelerate the economic growth and achieve the mission.

Keywords - Social Media Marketing, E -Commerce System, Consumer Behaviour, Purchasing Pattern, Businesses.

Introduction:

Social media marketing (SMM), also known as E-marketing or Digital marketing is the use of social media– or the social media platforms which helps the business or brands to connect with their potential customers. Key platforms of SMM include Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, X, etc to connect with the audience, which helps them to drive sales, promote their product, and increase exposure in a number of ways.

Consumer behavior is the comprehensive study of certain actions and mental processes, such as how people perceive a product in multiple ways and what leads them to buy a product. The research paper delves into the arena of consumer behavior with regards to SMM. By conducting the survey and collecting relevant data, the paper provides information about various elements that influence consumer behavior, such as whether people are likely to buy discounts in online platforms or In shops discount, effect of celebrity endorsement of the product, the effect of online reviews or ratings, video tutorials, ethical concerns of a brand, sustainability practices,

Augmented Reality(AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) in customer experiences, brands collaboration with college fest etc. Also, it talks about the vision of 2047.

Research Objectives:

1. To study the factors that lead to mutual interest among the consumer through the social media platform.
2. To study the intention of the consumer to have the online shopping media as its priority.
3. To study the data about how brands can improve their marketing strategies and adapt to the changing media landscape.

Literature Review:

Bhardwaj, S., & Koul, P. B. (2024).The study found how social media marketing can significantly influence consumers' purchase decisions. This influence may manifest in various ways, such as through targeted ads, influencer endorsements, or user-generated content.

Sharma. (2020, March). *A Study of Consumer Attitude Towards Online Shopping in India and Its Impact*, this research attempted to study the consumer's attitude towards online shopping and its impact, and found that factors such as easy access, on-time delivery, safe and secure payment process, a wide range of product availability, grievance handling system, easy return and replacing products influences and consumers' attitude towards online shopping.

Al-Dhuhli & Ismael (2013) The impact of social media on consumer buying behaviour: The research study found that recent trends indicate a shift toward Instagram over Facebook and Twitter(now X), particularly among Omani users. Instagram was preferred by most people for its interactive and engaging features, allowing buyers and sellers to communicate with each other using images, videos, etc

Pütter, M. (2017). The impact of social media on consumer buying intention. *Marketing*, 3(1), 7-13. The study found that companies are constantly looking for new methods and strategies for reaching consumers and for shaping consumer behaviours, including brand loyalty and intention to buy. A growing strategic focus is on the use of user-generated content, content that is created for specific brands which influences consumers perceptions.

Research Methodology:

The research study is completed through the method of primary Descriptive Research, and conceptual methodology. Through the comprehensive survey of 80 participants in the age range of 17-24 years it provides an overall comprehensive review of social media marketing influence on consumer behaviour through convenience sampling method. The subgroup selection has been a representation of the active users of social media. The data collected from the other research papers and case studies was done through a thematic analysis. In this analysis, the recurrence of the theme and patterns drawn through the statistical presentation led to a relevant conclusion. Through the utilisation of conceptual methodology, the variable relationship is justified through the existing theories producing similar outcomes like SET (Social Expectations Theory), TPV(Theory of Perceived Value.) and ECT (Expectation Confirmation Theory).The ECT (Expectation Confirmation theory) talks about consumer satisfaction dependent on social media factors, such as brand engagement, social reviews. Similarly, the SET theory (Social Exchange theory) and TPV(Theory of perceived value) express the evaluation of benefits and costs to interact with the brand perceived by the consumer.

The Conceptual Framework:

Through the comprehensive review and study of various research papers and case studies, the representation of the existing data, and theories have been analyzed to a structured set of important variables interconnected to each other. The research paper studies the relationship between social media marketing and the consumers purchasing pattern. Also, it provides the businesses the opportunity to market their brand through different strategies. The ECT (Expectation Confirmation Theory) talks about consumer satisfaction dependent on social media factors, such as brand engagement, social reviews. It also seeks to explain post-purchase or post-adoption satisfaction as a function of expectations, perceived performance, and disconfirmation of beliefs. Similarly, the SET theory (Social Exchange Theory) and TPV (Theory Of Perceived Value) express the evaluation of benefits and costs to interact with the brand perceived by the consumer is done through brand engagement. The theories state that a product's value to a consumer is influenced by the customer's subjective perception of its benefits, perceiving its worth trading off or not, influencing their buying decision.

Conceptual framework.

In this study, the dependent variable is consumer satisfaction through social media marketing (SMM) whereas the independent variables are social proof (likes, dislikes in social media platform), peer influence, and recommendations play a critical role in determining the satisfaction of a consumer. Positive feedback and recommendations from friends, family, or online reviews help in building trust and setting expectations, making customers more likely to perceive value in a product or service. Similarly, accessibility and ease of use for all demographics are vital. The emotional connection, loyalty, and trust consumers form with the brand help in interconnecting all these factors and so the executive happens. Also, independent variables like technological advancements, such as augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR), as well as innovative business strategies, significantly impact consumer satisfaction. Strategic branding efforts, as personalized marketing campaigns further enhance consumer engagement and foster satisfaction. By leveraging the execution of these independent variables effectively, businesses can create a lasting impression, influence purchase decisions, and ultimately drive a great consumer satisfaction as the outcome of these factors.

Analysis Section:

In this section, the evaluation and analysis of the survey questions has been done to know its main objectives and inclusive review.

Question No.	Question	Mostly preferable	Not preferable
1.	If given a choice between an online exclusive offer and an in-store discount for the same product, which would you choose ?	56.25%	43.75%
2.	How often online reviews or ratings influence your decision to purchase a product?	95%	5%
3.	Are you aware of the vr (virtual reality) technology and ar(Augmented reality) technology for better customer experience?	83.75%	16.25%
4.	How likely are you to purchase products or services from businesses that collaborate with or set up stalls at a college fest?	86.25%	13.75%

1 If given a choice between an online exclusive offer and an in-store discount for the same product, which would you choose ?

The pie chart (1.1) shows 56.25% of respondents prefer online exclusive offers over in-store discounts, whereas only 43.75% preferred in-store discounts, indicating a slight preference for discount shopping.

Pie chart 1.1

The part in blue represents online offer: 45 (56.25%)

The part in red represents In store discount : 35 (43.75%)

The pie chart (1.2) shows the impact of discounts on consumers shopping from a study on Indian buyers by the thesis of Centria university of applied. It shows 58.60 percent of people are influenced by discounts on online platforms.

Pie chart 1.2

2.How do often online reviews or ratings influence your decision to purchase a product?

The pie chart(1.3) shows that about 68.75 percent of people purchase after reading the review in written form or as per the tutorials available. Whereas only about 8.75 people purchase without having a look at reviews.

Pie chart 1.3

Part in blue represents Always: 27(33.75%)

Part in red represents Often: 28(35%)

Part in yellow represents Sometimes :21 (26.25%)

Part in green represents Rarely : 4(5%)

Part in purple represents Never: 0(0%)

The pie chart (1.4) shows the trust and safety for online shopping in customers in study on customer satisfaction by Archana Kumari. It shows that around 34 percent of people think online shopping is safe and secure.

Pie chart 1.4

3.Are you aware of vr (virtual reality) technology and ar(Augmented reality) technology for better customer experience?

In the below pie chart (1.5), from the survey of 80 participants to be aware of the latest technological advancements for a better experience in shopping is 83.75% (67).

Pie chart 1.5

The part in blue represents Yes: 67 (83.75%)

The part in red represents No: 13 (16.25%)

The table (1.6) the survey was conducted by the National Chung Hsing University, Taiwan. In order to get statistical data about the awareness and experience of Augmented reality (AR) and virtual Reality (VR) to the students. It shows that 70.22% of female and 29.19% of male are aware about it.

GENDER	RESPONSES	PERCENTAGE
MALE	197	29.19%
FEMALE	474	70.22%
OTHERS	4	0.59%
TOTAL	675	100%

Table 1 - Demographics of respondents.

Table 1.6

4. How likely are you to purchase products or services from businesses that collaborate with or set up stalls at a college fest?

The pie chart below (1.7) the possibility of consumer interaction if there is any business collaboration done in institutions is 32.5% (26%).

Pie chart 1.7

The part in red represents Somewhat Likely : 26(32.5%)

The part in blue represents Very Likely : 18(22.5%)

The part in yellow represents Neutral : 25(31.25%)

The part in green represents Very Unlikely : 9 (11.25%)

The part in purple represents Somewhat Unlikely: 2(2.5%)

The graph (1.8) shows a study using a questionnaire to analyze consumer behavior and views on Want Want's marketing strategy. The outcomes revealed that 90% of Recommendation willingness and 70% of packaging preferences could help the organisation optimize strategies to expand its consumer base sustainably.

Graph 1.8

Analysis of Snack consumption Trends and Brands.

Result and Discussion:

Objective 1(People preferability towards online shopping platforms):

The survey showed that most respondents prefer online offers over in-store discounts, aligning with findings from Centria University. Key reasons include convenience, flexible shopping hours, and the ability to compare prices across platforms, allowing consumers to save time, money, and effort.

Objective 2(The relationship with optimistic Range between consumer's trust with social reviews, proof , tutorials):

The survey of 80 respondents showed their reliance on online reviews before purchasing. Results showed that a majority of the population's portion rely on them. Compared to Archana Kumari's survey, this study reinforces how online reviews have become crucial in consumer decision-making, driven by trust in other customers' experiences.

Objective 3(To assess the level of awareness and potential influence of AR(augmented reality) and VR(virtual reality) in the field of consumer experience):

Out of total respondents, 83.75%(67) people were aware of technological advancement. Similar responses can be seen and considered in National Chung Hsing University, Taiwan. This also reveals how brands have incorporated AR and VR and are tapping into the potential for the same in the dynamic market.

Objective 4(The relationship between strategies by businesses in order to promote services or brand):

The survey results indicate that a significant portion of respondents are likely to purchase from businesses that collaborate with or set up stalls at college fests. Only a small percentage expressed disinterest. Similar trends were observed in Want Want's company survey, emphasizing that strong consumer interaction at such events enhances brand reputation and customer loyalty. This highlights the effectiveness of marketing strategies in college fests, particularly in targeting youth.

Objective 5 (The effect/influence of socio economic factor with decision making process of consumers):

The survey revealed that a notable portion of respondents acknowledge the influence of their social circle on purchasing decisions, while some experience occasional impact based on context. Others prefer making independent choices. Youth, in particular, may adjust their preferences to align with social groups, influencing their purchasing patterns.

Objective 6(Age range of 17-24 with most comfortable to showcase their interest with durability as their priority):

The survey showed that most respondents prefer classic products, valuing aesthetics and timeless appeal. A significant portion prioritizes durability, emphasizing quality, longevity, and cost-effectiveness. Only a small percentage opt for trendy products, highlighting a preference for staying updated with fashion and current styles.

Limitations:

Technological Dependence: Social media marketing depends on stable internet and technology. Weak connectivity, website glitches can reduce user engagement and affect business campaigns.

Regulatory Concerns: Privacy issues impact consumer trust. Users fear data misuse which makes them hesitant in engaging with brands.

Platform-Specific Analysis: While Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube are used widely, platforms like LinkedIn (professional networking) and Snapchat (AR filters) are underutilized. Businesses should optimize all channels for better outreach.

Implications:

The research explores how social media marketing influences consumer behavior (17-24 age group), enabling businesses to enhance strategies using online reviews, brand perception, and influencer marketing.

Ethical marketing is vital, businesses must align with regulations to ensure trust and long-term loyalty.

Adaptability is key. Platforms like Instagram evolve with features like reels and shopping options to meet evolving demands. Businesses should polish customer service and adopt AR & VR to stay competitive.

Suggestions:

1.Diversify Marketing Channels: In order to avoid over-dependence on a single platform, instead it should make use of other mediums such as email marketing, search engine optimization (SEO), and offline campaigns to boost social media efforts

2. Adoption of Niche Platforms: Leveraging the niche platforms like Pinterest for creatives and LinkedIn for B2B could expand reach and efficiently reach targeted audiences.

3.Build Ethical Marketing Practices: Focus on authentic content over intrusive ads to build consumer trust while integrating technology with ethical practices to adapt to meet with standard regulations.

Conclusion:

This research highlights the profound impact of social media on consumer behavior and its essential function in reshaping contemporary marketing approaches. The results indicate that elements such as social proof, endorsements from influencers, and reviews generated by users play a crucial role in establishing consumer trust and influencing purchasing choices. Social media platforms have become vital instruments for companies to engage with consumers through tailored and interactive communication. Nevertheless, the study also points out significant shortcomings, including a narrow emphasis on the diversity of platforms, the need for regulatory considerations, and the representation of marginalised groups. These insights highlight the necessity for inclusive, ethical, and flexible strategies to enhance the efficacy of social media marketing. By addressing these gaps and maximising the distinctive aspects of social media, businesses can strengthen trust, enhance customer loyalty, and sustain a competitive advantage in the rapidly changing digital arena.

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